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Location Identification and Capacity Determination of Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion Power Plants in Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

In many parts of the world, renewable energy-based power plants are gradually replacing fossil fuel-based power plants. Intermittency is a major issue for most of the renewable power plants. But Ocean Thermal Energy conversion plants (OTEC) can generate electricity throughout the day. Such plants are possible in tropical countries where the temperature difference between the surface and the depth of the water is sufficient for electricity generation. In this research, a pre-feasibility study of OTEC plants was carried out. The paper discussed the main requirements for OTEC plant location, different types of plants and their suitability, operation, and key advantages of existing plants especially in the South Asian region. Temperature versus sea depth and the distance from the seashore to the plant location were considered in identification of the suitable locations of the plant. Based on the criteria, three sites were identified as the most feasible locations for OTEC plants in the country: Pasikudha, Trincomalee, and Dondara. Plant capacity at each location has been calculated considering the enthalpy diagram. Plant capacity of each location has been presented as a trend line equation considering the power generated by the plant and the auxiliary power of the plant. The results of the study revealed that maximum possible power output of all the three plants is limited up-to 6 MW.

Keywords: Ocean Thermal Energy conversion, OTEC plant capacity, Renewable Energy, Sea depth,

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INRODUCTION

The basic principle of electricity generation from OTEC is to capture the temperature difference between the surface of the seawater and the depth of the ocean to produce steam to spin the turbine. This concept was first mentioned in Science Fiction by Jules Verne called "Twenty thousand Leagues under the Sea" published in 1870 (Kobayashi et al. 2001), (Fujita et al. 2018), (Vega 1999). The required temperature difference between the surface of the sea and the depth of the sea is mainly available in tropical countries around the globe (Ruiz et al., 2021), (Seungtaek et al., 2020). According to the World Ocean Atlas published by the United States National Ocean Centre in 2005, Sri Lanka is in a region that has about 22°C temperature difference between the surface and depth of the sea. Major advantage of OTEC power plants is their ability to generate electricity throughout the day. So, it does not have problem of intermittency that is the major drawback of renewables such as solar and wind.

Several studies have been carried out to investigate the feasibility of OTEC plants in South Asian region countries. Mohd Fahmie et al. carried out a preliminary design for constructing a 4 MW closed cycle OTEC power plant in Sabah, Malaysia (Fahmie et al. 2018). The study also included the OTEC plant potential in Malaysia is 100 MW. Jaswar Koto (Koto and Negara 2017) has studied the OTEC potential for electricity generation in Indonesia. Further, the study focused on the cost and performance of OTEC and showed that the plant cost beyond the capacity of 50 MW is much cheaper than the plant costs of smaller capacities. In the Philippines, a 10 MW OTEC plant has been in operation since 2008. In the world scenario, currently, there are two other power plants in operation. Since 2015, a 100 kW grid-connected closed-cycle OTEC power plant has been operating in the USA (Makai's Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) Power Plant, Hawaii 2020). A 100 W plant was built in Japan for demonstration purposes, and it has been in operation since 2013 (Okinawa OTEC Demonstration Facility 2023).

The operating principle of the OTEC plant is similar to the operation of any other conventional thermal power plant. The only difference is that the heat source used is the vertical temperature difference that exists in open tropical oceans. This temperature difference can be described as consisting of two layers separated by an interface. The upper layer of the seawater is heated by the sun and the temperature is mixed to depths of about 100 m because of the waves. The bottom layer consists of colder water of about 5°C formed at high latitudes. More often this temperature drop is gradual. The temperature difference between the upper and bottom layers can vary from 10 °C to 25 °C. The heat source and the heat sink required for a heat engine can be designed by that heat difference. The heat engine can be used to transform thermal energy into electrical. The temperature difference should be higher than 20°C to achieve net electrical power generation and good plant efficiency (Vega 2022).

The depth of the seabed with required temperature difference is one of the key parameters in deciding the feasibility of such a plant. Since submarine cables are used for cold-water transmission, the water at the selected depth should be accessible.

Different techniques have been proposed and experimented with to use a thermal gradient for electricity generation. At present, two systems are discussed mostly by their method of converting working fluid to vapor to spin the turbine (Etemadi et al. 2011): Closed Cycle and Open Cycle.

In the closed cycle OTEC process, warm seawater is drawn from the surface layer of the ocean into a heat exchanger (evaporator) to vaporize a liquid with a boiling point of about -30°C . Liquid propane and liquid ammonia have such low boiling points. The vapor drives a turbine that is connected to an electric generator. Exhaust vapor from the turbine is condensed in a second heat exchanger (condenser), which is cooled by deep seawater that is pumped from the deep ocean. The condensed vapor is then returned to the evaporator to complete a cycle. The operation of a closed-cycle OTEC plant can be modeled with the saturated Rankine cycle. In the past, the Rankine cycle preferred water as a working medium, and now most of the applications prefer to use the organic Rankine cycle having a working fluid with a low boiling point such as ammonia. OTEC's closed cycle operating mechanism is also based on the organic Rankine cycle since the temperature difference in OTEC is very small.

In an open-cycle OTEC system, the working fluid is warmed seawater itself. A fraction of the warm seawater is flash evaporated below its saturation value. Then, that steam is expanded through a low-pressure turbine that is coupled with a generator. The steam leaving the turbine is then condensed by cold deep seawater through a cold-water pipe (Vega 2013). There are some special conditions to be considered when planning an open-cycle OTEC plant. The system must be properly sealed to maintain the system in a partial vacuum ranging from about 3% to 1% atmospheric pressure. Components should be larger enough to prevent steam velocities to get dangerously high velocities because the specific volume of the low-pressure steam is larger than the pressurized warm water. Therefore, the designed plant may be larger in the open cycle process-based plants. In this process, the evaporator produces desalinated steam. Therefore, when the steam is condensed, fresh drinkable water can be obtained if a surface condenser is used.

The thermodynamic model and the operating principle of the open cycle OTEC heat engine, with its environment, can be stated as parallel to the Rankine cycle. In this condition, the role of the discharge pump and the non-condensable gas compressor is assumed as the role of the Rankine cycle pump (Vega 2013). There are three types of OTEC power plants based on the location of operation.

Land-based plants: Plants that are constructed in locations such as those with narrow shelves, steep (15°C - 20°C) offshore slopes, and relatively smooth sea floors come under land-based power plants. Such plants prevent sophisticated monitoring and extensive maintenance associated with an open-ocean environment.

Shelf-based plants: Plants that are mounted to the continental shelf at depths up to 10,000 ft are known as shelf-based plants. A shelf-mounted plant is towed to the site and attached to the sea bottom. Such plants help to have closer access to the deep seawater and avoid turbulent surf zones.

Floating power plants: Floating OTEC plants are offshore plants mounted on a floating platform. Such plants are designed for large-capacity power plants. Stabilizing such plants has difficulties.

In the past, an OTEC plant was recommended for Sri Lanka after the analysis on bathymetry, thermal resources, resources, mixed layer depth, weather conditions, and sea & swell conditions and recommended (U.S. Department of Energy 1989), (U.S. Department of Energy 1979). Only a few studies were done on the feasibility of OTEC plant for Sri Lanka. The first preliminary study on the feasibility of the OTEC plant was carried out by Sri Lanka National Science Council (National Science Council 1980) in 1980 and the report concluded that such plants are technically feasible but economically not viable. This study was carried out forty years ago and the present status in the

energy sector of the country has significantly changed. In 1994, the National Aquatic Resources Research and Development Agency (NARA) carried out a study on a conceptual design of OTEC in Sri Lanka. The study has proposed to have a floating-type OTEC power plant in the country. Meegahapola L et.al (Meegahapola et al. 2017) have discussed strategies and challenges of OTEC in Sri Lanka. The paper also discussed the financial aspects of such OTEC plants. The above studies were carried out for more than 10-15 years ago, and since then, the technology has been advanced and the equipment costs of such plants have been reduced (Kobayashi et al. 2001), (Seungtaek et al. 2020). In the meantime, the generation cost of fossil fuel-based power plants has been increased due to incorporating penalty costs for environmental effects (Choi et al. 2023, Holechek et al. 2022). More importantly, now the world is more concerned about environmental protection, and the prevention of greenhouse gas emissions. Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify locations and capacity of OTEC power plants in Sri Lanka.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Key Parameters for Site Location

The best possible location of the OTEC power plant is determined based on three parameters: Temperature Difference, The distance of the thermal gradient column from the shore, and Depth of the deep cold water

Temperature difference between the surface temperature and temperature of the layer at the depth of 750 - 1500 m is used for electricity generation. The minimum value of temperature difference that is required for energy conversion is 18°C.

The distance of the thermal gradient column from the shore is mainly responsible for the cost of the plant and therefore the unit cost. When the thermal gradient column is far away from the shore, both the costs of the piping system and cabling under the depth of the sea for power transmission become expensive.

Water pumps are required for pumping the water from the seabed. The power consumed by these water pumps depends on the depth of the cold water. This power is a major portion of the auxiliary power of the plant and has a greater influence on the net power output of the plant.

2.2 Site Selection.

After studying data available in NARA (sea depth and distance from sea shore) and in the report on "Overview of Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion" (Madhawa,2000), three potentially suitable locations were chosen for further analysis. Considering the temperature difference of surface water and the deep-sea water and the distance from the sea to the potential locations, three sites have been identified.

2.2.1 Site 1: Pasikudah - (7.9865N, 81.7614E): Pasikudah is located 35 km northwest of Batticaloa district in the eastern province. The location is very famous for its beautiful beach. The temperature profile of the location is shown in Figure 1 (a). According to the graph shown in Figure 1(a), the temperature on the surface of the seawater is about 29°C, and at 500 m depth, the temperature becomes 10°C. This means the temperature difference of 19°C occurs even at a depth of 500 m. The distance from the seashore to the site is about 5.5 km as shown in Figure 2(a).

2.2.2 Site 2: Trincomalee- (8°36.10N, 81°17.43E): Trincomalee is located on Sri Lanka's northern coast. Stretching on either side of a narrow peninsular, it is flanked by some of the most idyllic white-sand beaches in Sri Lanka. The beach has been a tourist destination for many years. The proposed site is near Trincomalee Bay. The temperature profile of the seawater is given in Figure

1(b). As per the figure 1(b), site 2 (8°36.10N, 31°17.43E) has a surface temperature of about 27°C and a cold seawater temperature of about 6°C at 1100 m depth. Since the temperature difference is about 21°C, Trincomalee Bay is suitable for an OTEC plant. The distance from Trincomalee Beach to the identified location is 35.1 km (Figure 2(b)).

2.2.3 Site 3: Dondra - (5.783333N, 80.50E) Dondra is a settlement on the extreme southernmost tip of Sri Lanka, in the Indian Ocean near Matara, Southern Province, Sri Lanka. As per the temperature profile shown in Figure 1(c), the surface temperature is about 29°C and the temperature at about 1300 m depth is about 6°C. The temperature difference of 23°C exists at the distance. Therefore, the proposed site is also suitable to locate an OTEC plant. The distance between the location and Dondra is 18.1 km (Figure 2(c)).

The depth of the cold water has a greater influence on the cost of the plant. The cost is increasing with the deepening of the cold water. When the cold water is at a greater depth, it is required to have high-capacity water pumps. The cost of these water pumps and associated installation works becomes expensive. It is possible to build a low-cost power plant when the required temperature gradient is available at about 500 m-1500 m depth.

Figure1: Temperature versus depth of the sea of three locations (source: NARA)

(a) Pasikudah

(b) Trincomalee

(c) Dondara

Figure 2: Possible location for OTEC

In sites 1,2 and 3, the cold water of the required temperature is available at the sea depths of 500 m, 1000 m, and 1200 m respectively. This means all the three sites are suitable for the OTEC power plants.

2.3 Plant Type Selection

The distance from the seashore to the deep cold seawater extraction point would restrict the feasibility of an onshore plant. This is because of the increase of the capital cost for cold water pipes with the increase of the distance and associated reduction in thermodynamic efficiency. Considering the distance to the seashore from the selected sites (18.1 km, 22.5 km, 33.1 km) an offshore platform (floating) type plant has been proposed.

The selection between open-cycle and closed-cycle types of the plant depends on the required capital investment and the plant capacity. The cost for the main components of two types of plants based on their capacities is given in Table 1 (Seungtaek et al., 2020). As per the table, constructing an open cycle plant requires higher capital cost, therefore considering the predicted capacity of the plant closed cycle plant is recommended.

2.4 Plant Capacity calculation

In this study, plant capacities were estimated by considering only the temperature difference. The exact plant capacity can be determined after analyzing the characteristics of elements of the plant (condenser, evaporator, etc.), site parameters, environmental parameters, climatic parameters, etc. The plant capacity of a closed-cycle type plant was calculated using mathematical formulae and data from various sources. The T-S diagram is shown in Figure 03. The numbers indicated in the diagram and the status of the working fluid in the closed-cycle power plant shown in Figure 4 are the same.

2.4 Plant Capacity calculation.

Figure 3: Enthalpy diagram

The total heat output from the evaporator after absorbing the heat of the warm seawater can be calculated using the equation (1) respectively (Yeh et al. 2005).

Figure 4: Closed-Cycle OTEC plant

$$Q_e = \dot{m}_{WS} C \Delta T_{WS} \quad (1)$$

Considering the energy balance, the mass flow rate of saturated vapor can be calculated using equation (2) (Yeh et al. 2005).

$$\dot{m}_a = \frac{Q_e}{(h_1 - h_4)} \quad (2)$$

Assuming that the expansion of saturated vapor of the working fluid into low pressure's mixture of saturated vapor and liquid happens is entropically, the working fluid that is leaving from the turbine is calculated using the equation (3) respectively (Engels et al. 2014)

$$x = \frac{(S_g(at\ 10^\circ C) - S_f(at\ 10^\circ C))}{S_{fg}(at\ 10^\circ C)} \quad (3)$$

The enthalpy of the working fluid vapor at the turbine output is calculated using the equation (4) respectively (Engels et al. 2014)

$$h_2 = h_f(at\ 10^\circ C) + x h_{fg}(at\ 10^\circ C) \quad (4)$$

Since the enthalpy at the input and output of the turbine are known, total electric work resulting from turbine-generator unit is calculated using the equation (5) (Yeh et al. 2005).

$$W_{tg} = \dot{m}_a (h_1 - h_2) \eta_t \eta_g \quad (5)$$

2.4.1 Auxiliary power of the plant

The net output of the generator differs from W_{tg} given in equation (5) because of the plant's auxiliary power. Power consumption by the plant is mainly because of the pumps' operations. The pumps are mainly required for three purposes: pumping of deep seawater to the condenser; pumping of the warm seawater to the evaporator; and pumping of the working fluid to the evaporator (Engels et al. 2014). These pumps are identified as cold seawater pump, working fluid pump, and warm seawater pump. The auxiliary power of the OTEC plants is high due to the power consumed by these pumps. The depth of the sea that has the required temperature difference has a greater impact on the capacity of the pumps and therefore the auxiliary power of the plant.

Power consumed by the working fluid circulating pump, warm seawater pump, and cold seawater pump are given in equations (6), (7), and (8) respectively (Engels et al. 2014).

$$W_p = v(P_4 - P_3) \dot{m}_a / \eta_{ap} \quad (6)$$

$$W_{wsp} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \dot{m}_{ws} v_{ws}^2}{\eta_{wsp}} \quad (7)$$

$$W_{cp} = H_{(loss)} \dot{m}_{cs} g / \eta_{csp} \quad (8)$$

The net output power of the generator is calculated after deducting power consumed by the three pumps are given in equations (6), (7), and (8), This is given in equation (9)

$$W_n = W_{tg} - W_{ap} - W_{ws} - W_{cs} \quad (9)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Power output from the proposed three sites was calculated using the equations (1) – (9) and the data of the three sites are given in figures (2)-(4). The data relevant to the condenser, evaporator pipe, and parameters of the pumps were taken from Yeah et al (2005) (Yeh et al. 2005). These data are summarized in Table 1. Ammonia was chosen as a working fluid for all three sites. Enthalpy (h) and entropy (s) of the saturated ammonia (liquid-vapor) at 23 °C and 10 °C were obtained from the

physical properties of the ammonia (Haar and Gallagher 1978). Accordingly, $h_1=h_2=h_g(23\text{ }^\circ\text{C})=1461.933\text{ kJ/kg}$; $h_3=h_4=h_f(10\text{ }^\circ\text{C})=5.508\text{ kJ/kg}$; $S_1=S_g(23\text{ }^\circ\text{C})=5.0508\text{ kJ/kg}$; $S_3=S_f(10\text{ }^\circ\text{C})=0.8769\text{ kJ/kg}$. As per the thermodynamic formula, the pressure at points 1,2,3 and 4 were: $P_1=P_4=P(23\text{ }^\circ\text{C})=943.96\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $P_2=P_3=P(10\text{ }^\circ\text{C})=615.29\text{ kPa}$. The volume at the fluid state was $0.0016\text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$.

Table 1: Seawater, turbine, and pump data of the proposed sties

Parameter	Dondra	Trincomalee	Pasikudah
specific heat of the sea water (C)		4.8 kJ/kg ⁰ C	
Warm seawater inlet temperature	27 ⁰ C	29 ⁰ C	29 ⁰ C
Warm seawater outlet temperature	25 ⁰ C	27 ⁰ C	27 ⁰ C
Cold seawater inlet temperature	6 ⁰ C	6 ⁰ C	6 ⁰ C
Cold seawater outlet temperature	7 ⁰ C	7 ⁰ C	7 ⁰ C
Desired ammonia temperature at the evaporator outlet	25 ⁰ C	25 ⁰ C	25 ⁰ C
Desired ammonia temperature at the condenser outlet	10 ⁰ C	10 ⁰ C	10 ⁰ C
Seawater pipe diameters(both)	1 m	1 m	1 m
Turbine efficiency		89%	
Generator efficiency		96%	
Seawater pump efficiency (both)		85%	
Ammonia pump efficiency		85%	
The kinematic velocity of the seawater (K)		$1.83 \times 10^{-6}\text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	
ξ Approximate pipe roughness		20 mm	
Cold seawater depth	1300 m	1100 m	600 m

By using the above equations and the data, the variations of power (W_{net} , W_{total} , W_p , W_{wsp} , W_{csp}) versus mass flow rate of warm seawater were plotted and shown in Figure 5

For the considered site parameters, the maximum power that can be generated was determined using the trend line equations for each site separately. The trend line equations and maximum net power output of respective sites are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Maximum power generation of proposed sites

	Trend line equation	Maximum possible power output (MW)
Pasikudah	$y = -2 * 10^{-8}x^2 + 0.0005x - 0.6297$	2.49
Trincomalee	$y = -3 * 10^{-8}x^2 + 0.0005x - 0.4816$	1.60
Dondara	$y = -3 * 10^{-8}x^2 + 0.0005x - 0.4345$	1.65

By considering all three outputs it can be determined that the Pasikudah site has the potential to generate electricity more than the other two sites. The reason is that the cold-water intake depth is shallower in the site than in the other two. The graphs also showed the impact of the depth of the cold water on the net output of the plant. When the depth of the cold water is greater the pump capacities and the power consumed by the pumps are higher.

(x)

(y)

(z)

Figure 5 (x), (y), (z): Power variation of the three sites with the warm water

Therefore, even though the power generated by the plant is high the net power output becomes less.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that the construction of OTEC plants in Sri Lanka is technically feasible. The results of calculations show that the maximum possible power output of these three plants is only 5.74 MW.

The main barrier to further increase of the power output is the power consumed by the pumps of the plant. It is possible to connect these plants to the distribution network and serve as distributed generators. The economy of such a connection depends on the proximity of the grid. This is because of the cost involved in transmission of the power generated by the plant to a substation (cost of the cables and accessories, cable laying under the sea etc.). Another option is to consider these plants to form microgrids. Microgrids are now increasingly used for providing electricity to distribution systems by utilizing available renewable sources of energy in respective areas or regions. All these three locations are very famous tourist destinations. OTEC can be used not only for electricity generation but to provide cool water and air conditioning which are very much required for the tourist hotels in the area., the tourist industry looks for state assistance due to energy and financial crisis. This study did not include details of the economic analysis of OTEC plants. However, recent studies have shown that the levelized cost of energy of low and medium-scale OTEC power plants is around 0.3 USD per kWh (Chenglong Xio and Raza Gufam, 2023). At present, the unit cost of energy from the diesel and furnace oil is a little higher than this value. However, it also should be considered that the lack of foreign currency to export the fuel and the environmental pollution due to the operation of diesel power plants. Therefore, OTEC power plants can be one of the candidates to meet the 100% power generation from renewable energy sources in the future.

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NOMENCLATURE

Q	The total heat flow (<i>kw</i>)	U	Velocity(<i>m/s</i>)
\dot{m}	mass flow rate(<i>kg/hr</i>)	W	Electric work(<i>kw</i>)
c	Specific heat of seawater(<i>kJ/kg</i>)	S	Entropy (<i>kJ/kg</i>)
T	Temperature (<i>K</i>)	x	The quality of ammonia vapor leaving the turbine
h	Enthalpy (<i>kJ/kg</i>)		

SUBSCRIPTIONS

e	evaporator	p	Pump
c	Condenser	g	Gas
ws	warm sea water	f	Fluid
cs	cold sea water	a	Ammonia
tg	turbine generator unit		

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